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Design, Analysis and Optimization of Four Degrees of Freedom of Parallel Gripper Mechanism for Industrial Automation

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Abstract

Objectives: To obtain the positions, velocities, and acceleration of actuators of the 4-DOF of the parallel gripper, and optimization of the mechanism is carried out to find the optimal dimensions of the mechanism. **Methods:** Kinematic analysis is carried out to find the positions and velocities of the gripper of the mechanism. The method used to solve the position of the mechanism is inverse kinematics. A source code is written in MATLAB software to find the positions and velocities of the gripper. This software is a computing platform which can solve large size matrices easily which is most suitable for robots. A model of the mechanism is created in CATIA with constraints. The developed CATIA model is used in ANSYS software for structural analysis. The method used for finding optimal dimensions is Genetic algorithms. Optimization is carried out using Genetic Algorithms (GA's) using the Energy Manipulation Index as an objective for obtaining the optimal dimensions of the parallel gripper mechanism. Finally, ADAMS software is used to simulate the mechanism. **Findings:** using inverse kinematic equations the results of displacements, velocities, and accelerations obtained for in-plane horizontal motion, and in-plane vertical motion s plotted. After checking the gripper performance, It is observed that the in-plane vertical transmission is better than the in-plane horizontal transmission. Based on the Energy Manipulation Index (EMI), the performance-to-effort ratio of the gripper object is calculated. It tells about the physical significance of energy transfer efficiency. If the energy occupied by the end-effector is higher than the 4-DOF Parallel Gripper achieves higher efficiency and possesses better manipulability performance. Maximum EMI is taken as an objective for optimization using GA. Simulation is carried out using ADAMS software to determine the driving forces or torques. **Novelty/improvement:** In this paper the performance index EMI is taken as objective to find the optimal dimensions of the 4-DOF of parallel gripper.

Keywords: DOF parallel gripper; Inhand manipulation; Inhand twisting; Driving force; Energy Manipulation Index (EMI)

1 Introduction

The thumb is a vital component of both natural and prosthetic hands, essential for grasping and manipulating objects⁽¹⁾ the gripper is in all directions; to replicate the functionality of a natural hand, a prosthetic hand's design must enable the thumb to move in multiple directions. This innovative thumb, along with the entire prosthetic hand, closely resembles human hand proportions but with significantly reduced weight. The thumb offers impressive mechanical compliance and excels in various grasping tasks. With a unique dual-mode operation and a single actuator, this soft thumb provides versatile grasping capabilities, including abduction/adduction and flexion/extension. By minimizing the number of actuators required, we reduce space and power consumption and flexibility. Sylvain et al.⁽²⁾ examine on soft robotic hands provide a basic primitive of hand manipulation in the existence of uncertainty.

E. Zheng and W. Zhang in their research work⁽³⁾ introduced a fresh design concept for a robotic end effector showcasing a multi-fingered under-actuated gripper capable of executing parallel and self-adaptive (PASA) grasping. By incorporating an eccentric cam into a modified four-bar linkage mechanism, the design enables the fingers to compensate for the standard gap distance encountered during parallel pinching. Further, enhances the gripper's ability to grasp objects against surfaces and in confined spaces. Experimental validation with a finger prototype confirms the desired closing trajectory. Wang, L., et al.⁽⁴⁾ Generalized parallel mechanisms featuring a customizable moving platform have gained popularity in the field of parallel mechanism research. Such gripper mechanisms are well-suited for grasping large or heavy objects in challenging and hazardous environments unsuitable for human intervention. This research introduces a novel family of gripper mechanisms with (3+2+1) degrees of freedom (three translations, two rotations, and an additional grasping motion) based on generalized parallel mechanisms with a customizable moving platform. The design incorporates a closed-loop configurable moving platform optimized for grasping tasks. Jie Zhao et al.⁽⁵⁾ In their early work, a four degrees-of-freedom (DOF) Parallel Manipulator (PM) with a 4PPa-2PaR configuration was proposed to generate 3-DOF Translational and 1-DOF Rotational (3T1R) motions. It was noted for its advantages of symmetric geometry, simple kinematics, and infinite extension of translational workspace along its linear guide direction. An optimization algorithm based on the Genetic Algorithm was proposed to maximize the reachable workspace, resulting in a significant increase in the workspace. Finally, a prototype of the M-type PM was fabricated to validate the effectiveness of the modified design. Zuo, S., et al.⁽⁶⁾ In their study, a novel four-degrees-of-freedom parallel gripper, with potential applications in industrial automation, is presented. The gripper employs a parallel grasping mode on objects and is capable of independently executing in-plane horizontal and vertical motions, as well as in-hand twisting motion. Kinematic and dynamic models of the gripper-object system are developed, and the controllable internal force acting on the object is calculated to minimize driving force/torque. Numerical simulations include a comparison between the MATLAB model and the ADAMS model to validate the motion capabilities of the parallel gripper and the rationality of analytical modeling studies. Kashef S R, et al.⁽⁷⁾ the mechanical design of an artificial finger is recognized as the critical determinant of prosthetic hand performance. In pursuit of a simple, dexterous, and functional bionic hand, it has been argued by researchers that two primary requirements should be integrated into the development of artificial fingers: (i) an anthropomorphic structure and (ii) the capability to grasp objects securely and reliably. The existing body of literature on various performance criteria for prosthetic fingers is initially reviewed in this paper. These criteria are categorized into (a) grasp and (b) physical characteristics. Different aspects of prosthetic finger features, including shape adaptability, natural motion, stability, force isotropy, workspace, and weight, are considered based on perspectives from existing literature. To this end, relevant articles published between 2000 and 2019 were searched, resulting in the selection and assessment of 28 linkage-driven mechanisms from approximately 280 papers, according to the performance criteria. Finally, in line with the intended use of a prosthetic hand, several key considerations necessary for developing an anthropomorphic artificial finger are suggested in this paper. Zhong et al.⁽⁸⁾ proposed a novel soft pneumatic dexterous gripper that consists of four soft fingers and a movable sucker. Compared with rigid dexterous hands and other soft grippers, the soft pneumatic dexterous gripper has four convertible grasping modes. W. Haouas, et al.⁽⁹⁾ In many applications, two-fingered manipulation robotic systems are widely utilized, especially at small scales. A commonly employed approach involves attaching a gripper to a robot. In this paper, a new mechanism with eight degrees of freedom (DOF) intended for two-fingered dexterous manipulation is introduced. A prototype is utilized to manipulate and insert a 2-mm screw. K. Wen et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ A novel spatial hybrid parallel robot with 6+3 degrees of freedom (DOF) and a 3-[R(RR-RRR) SR] kinematic redundant configuration, featuring revolute actuators, is proposed. A novel design⁽¹¹⁾ for a robotic end-effector is presented in this paper. The design is focused on a 4-DOF parallel gripper with potential applications in industrial automation. Comprising two parallelogram mechanisms and two grasp sliders, this gripper enables in-hand twisting action (in-hand manipulation) as well as in-plane horizontal and vertical transmission. The gripper can facilitate horizontal transmission to complement the robot arm's workspace, and it exhibits relatively superior performance in in-hand manipulation and in-plane vertical transmission. Dionisis et al.⁽¹²⁾ discussed the design and employed a high-speed electro-mechanical robotic gripper for grasping and manipulation of

objects. The novelty of the developed robot end-effector lies in the ability to perform rapid and precise in-hand manipulation of different environments. I-Ting Chi et al. ⁽¹³⁾ developed a compliant gripper using topology synthesis and a dimensional synthesis approach. A Kinematic model is used for force-displacement analysis based on the chained beam constraint model.

Xiaodong Jin et al. ⁽¹⁴⁾ in this work focus on designing dexterous hands based on parallel finger structures to improve dexterity, carrying capability, and high precision. Kinematics of the fingers are obtained for knowing the workspace. The finger structures of RR-RPR and 2-UU-UPU are presented by structural evolution from the well-known PMs of parallelogram and 3-UU by means of group deduction, respectively. Two three-finger dexterous hands are designed by assembling the obtained parallel fingers on the palm in the same direction. The in-hand configurations are hybrid mechanisms, whose motion properties are analyzed by equivalent to the parallel mechanisms (PMs). For any mechanisms first, we need to find the positions of the actuators and end-effector using inverse or forward kinematics. S.S. Ganesh et al. found inverse kinematics for 2-DOF parallel kinematic mechanisms and carried out optimization using GA ⁽¹⁵⁾.

The shortcomings of this literature survey, it is understood that various types of grippers like soft grippers, dexterous grippers, in-hand grippers, passive grippers, etc., move with good accuracy in grasping objects. When the length and radius of the object become smaller or larger, the industrial grippers mentioned above can no longer keep a parallel grasping and thus produce failed twisting due to the insufficient frictional force, and incorrect grasping position caused by excessive force. To overcome this issue and supplement the selection of gripper, this works out a 4-DOF parallel gripper with a symmetric structure, in which a parallelogram mechanism is used and the grasp slider can be performed vertical motion relative to the finger. This gripper can perform not only in-hand twisting motion but also in-plane horizontal and vertical motion.

In this work, the research gap is filled by considering four degrees of freedom parallel gripper which is well suited for holding the objects by the end effector. This mechanism has good accuracy for holding smaller or bigger radius objects. The mathematical model for kinematic analysis is done to find the positions and velocities of the mechanism. The performance index is developed for knowing the performance of the mechanism.

In this paper, kinematic analysis is done for finding the position of actuators. Secondly, modeling of the 4-DOF parallel gripper is done in CATIA and optimization is done using GA Based on energy manipulation index (EMI). Maximum of EMI is taken as an objective for optimization using GA.

1.1 Structure of the Gripper

The parallel gripper possesses two identical grasp units that adopt a symmetrical arrangement with a simple configuration. The main structure as shown in Figure 3, of each grasp unit is a parallelogram mechanism that contains the medial link (links A_1D_1 and A_2D_2), lateral link (links B_1C_1 and B_2C_2), and L-shaped link (links $C_1D_1H_1$ and $C_2D_2H_2$); a grasp slider performs vertical motion relative to the link D_1H_1 (D_2H_2) of the L shaped link. The driving torques and forces are applied to active joints A_1 and A_2 , and active joints E_1 and E_2 , respectively. The L-shaped link and the grasp slider constitute the output end of the parallel gripper and collectively complete the gripping task and transportation task (i.e., in-plane horizontal and vertical transmission, as well as in-hand manipulation) of the objects with different sizes and different shapes via respective actuators. Specifically, active joints A_1 and A_2 are used to determine the horizontal and a small number of vertical positions of the L-shaped links, and then accomplish object gripping and in-plane horizontal transmission. The in-hand manipulation (i.e., in-hand twisting motion) and main in-plane vertical transmission can be easily realized via the coupling motion of grasp sliders (i.e., active joints E_1 and E_2).

2 Methodology

2.1 Formulation of work

In accordance with the structural feature of the parallel gripper, and its CATIA model as shown in Figure 1 the posture of the center point F of the object in the base coordinate system O-XY can be represented as

$$X_F = X_{A1} + l_1 \cos \theta_1 + l_{E1F} \quad (1)$$

$$X_F = X_{A1} + l_2 \cos \theta_2 - l_{E1F} \quad (2)$$

$$\theta_F = \frac{s_{arc}}{R} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_F = l_1 \sin\theta_1 + s_1 + s_{E1G1} + s_{arc} \tag{4}$$

$$Y_F = l_1 \sin\theta_2 + s_2 + s_{E2G2} - s_{arc} \tag{5}$$

Fig 1. Schematic diagram and CATIA model of 4-DoF parallel gripper mechanism

The velocity mapping relationship between 2 contact points (G_1 & G_2) and center point F of the object can be written as

$$V_{G1X} = V_{FX} \tag{6}$$

$$V_{G1Y} = V_{FY} - R\dot{\theta}_F \tag{7}$$

$$V_{G2X} = V_{FX} \tag{8}$$

$$V_{G2Y} = V_{FY} + R\dot{\theta}_F \tag{9}$$

$$\dot{X}^F = G\dot{u} \tag{10}$$

Where $\dot{X}^F = (V_{G1X}, V_{G1Y}, V_{G2X}, V_{G2Y})$ is the velocity vector of the contact point that is fixed to the object, expressed in the base coordinate system O-XY; $u = (V_{FX}, V_{FY}, \theta_F)$ denotes the output object velocity vector with respect to the base coordinate system O-XY; G is the grasp matrix.

2.2 Design of 4-DOF Parallel Gripper

The parallel gripper is modeled in CATIA and analysis is performed using ANSYS. In analysis of 4-DOF of parallel gripper the mesh element used is tetrahedron. The meshing model is shown in Figure 3 in the results and discussion section.

2.3 Numerical simulation of 4-DOF Parallel Gripper

Let us consider the parallel gripper of active medial links attached to the actuator, assuming that the gripper moves from the initial position and orientation to another position to observe the in-plane horizontal displacement with good position accuracy and flexible impact. Here assuming that the actuator is rotating in cycloid motion on the cam mechanism. While rotating the actuators the active medial links which are attached to the L-shaped links move the object assuming from the initial position to some extent. Here, the cycloid motion rotates 360 degrees for one revolution moves the object from its initial position and for another revolution the object back to its initial position.

2.4 ADAMS simulation

Dynamic modeling is performed by using ADAMS simulation. Here take the dimensions of the parallel gripper and sketch the model in ADAMS view. Giving all the connections go to the motion box to give major motion to the connection. Go to the simulation option to observe the gripper mechanism. Now go to post processing to take out the plots of the joints and X Forms of the dynamic mechanism. Moreover, in dynamic verification additionally, we can obtain the required drive forces or torque curves. The design of the parallel gripper in ADAMS view is shown in Figure 2.

Fig 2. Design of parallel gripper in ADAMS view and Model created in ADAMS

2.5 Design optimization

The design problem can be expressed as a standard optimization problem with design variables, constraints, and objectives. An attempt to find the optimal design to provide performance characteristics. The design variables considered for optimal design are L1 and L2 and the maximum of EMI is taken as an objective for optimization using GA. The variables are the parameters of the gripper medial link and L-shaped link.

Energy Manipulation Index (EMI):

The performance-to-effort ratio EMI⁽⁶⁾ is defined as

$$EMI = \frac{\dot{q}^T T^{-1} W_u T^{-1} \dot{q}}{\dot{q}^T W_q \dot{q}} \quad (11)$$

where $T = J^{-1}G$ denotes the transformation matrix between the input joint vector and the output object vector.

J is the jacobian matrix

W_u and W_q are the weighing matrices

In this the length matrix or unit matrix is used as the weighting matrix i.e. mass-inertia matrix is the weighting matrix, and then Equation (11) tells about the physical significance of energy transfer efficiency. If the energy occupied by the end-effector is higher than the 4-DOF Parallel Gripper achieves higher efficiency and possesses better manipulability performance.

Genetic Algorithm (GA): Genetic Algorithm depends on the concept of natural genetics and natural selection. The basic elements of natural genetics are reproduction, crossover, and, mutation is used in the genetic search procedure the advantage of using GA is that it can find a global optimum solution with a high probability in most cases.

Optimization process of GA:

1. In these, solutions from one population are taken and used to form a new population.
2. Offsprings or new solutions are formed based on their fitness values.
3. The above process is repeated until the condition is satisfied.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results for numerical analysis using ANSYS

In the ANSYS workbench after giving connections to the joints the gripper sets to run for the solution to evaluation results. In transient structural, insert the rotation to joint loads of active medial links and change the angle (in deg) for each deformation result. Insert the displacement load for grasp sliders for translation about the z-axis direction. Force is applied at the gripper hand to obtain stress values. The mesh model and deformation results of the parallel gripper using ANSYS are shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3. Deformation of the parallel gripper

The deformation results were obtained by solving the mesh model as shown in Table 1. Here, the deformation gradually decreases while mesh elements increase while changing the mesh size.

Table 1. Deformation at various mesh elements

S.NO	MESH (mm)	NODES	ELEMENTS	DEFORMATIONS (mm)
1	15	7165	2961	23.833
2	13	8424	3572	19.121
3	10	9268	3725	18.331
4	8	10574	4222	14.373
5	6	13854	5915	9.597
6	4	21903	8123	9.589
7	2	69098	24984	9.502

3.2 Stress evaluation of the object

In transient structural, insert displacement joint load or boundary condition to the grasp slider. The displacement is about 20mm to the grasp sliders to hold and move the object vertically. To the object, gradually increase the loads(N) to get the stress constant. Finally, the solution can be converging at max stress value. Figure 4 and Table 2 show the results of stresses obtained at various loads. The max stress value obtained is equal to 2269.6Mpa.

Fig 4. Stress evaluation using ANSYS for various loads

Table 2. Stresses at various loads

S.NO	LOAD (N)	STRESS (MPa)
1	200	569.5
2	400	1137.8
3	600	1704.5
4	800	2065.25
5	1000	2248.72
6	1200	2269.6

3.3 Results of parallel gripper in MATLAB simulation

To verify the kinematic and dynamic modelling, a numerical evaluation is carried out to obtain the positions, velocities and acceleration of actuators of the gripper. The task is to accomplish in-plane horizontal motion, in-plane vertical motion. The results of displacements, velocities, and accelerations obtained for in-plane horizontal motion, in-plane vertical motion s plotted in Figure 5

Fig 5. Results of displacements, velocities, and accelerations using MATLAB for in-plane horizontal motion, in-plane vertical motion

3.4 Result of parallel gripper dynamically in ADAMS view

In-plane horizontal motion curves:

Model of 4 DOF of the parallel gripper is created in ADAMS software and the variation of displacements, velocities, and acceleration in plane horizontal and vertical motion is plotted as shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. After simulating the gripper

model proceed to post processing to carry out the variation plots obtained from the results. The variation curves are generated to obtain the position accuracy without rigid and flexible impacts.

Fig 6. Variation curve of displacement, velocity, and acceleration in plane horizontal motion

Fig 7. Variation curve of displacement, velocity, and acceleration in plane vertical motion

3.5 Results of design optimization of the parallel gripper

Based on the energy manipulation index (EMI), the performance-to-effort ratio of the gripper object is calculated along with the transportation of the object. Maximum of EMI is taken as an objective for optimization using GA. Table 3 shows the optimum design variables and its corresponding EMI is 0.01226 and its convergence of GA is achieved after 50 generations as shown in Figure 8.

The results obtained are compared with the literature⁽⁶⁾. The results and simulation obtained show that the gripper has good horizontal transmission in the workspace. The mechanism shows good performance in-hand manipulation and in-plane vertical transmission. A new performance index (Energy Manipulation Index) is used for optimization.

Table 3. Variables considered for optimization

Design variables	Symbols	Length (mm)
Length of the medial link	L1	40
Length of the L-shaped link	L2	123

Fig 8. Convergence of GA

4 Conclusion

A CAD model of a parallel gripper is sketched in CATIA V5 and it is imported to ANSYS workbench for analysis. The grasping forces between the slider are done to check the deformation of the object. The deformation is gradually constant at 24984 mesh elements. Deformation gets constant at 9.502 mm Stress evaluation is carried out in ANSYS workbench. The maximum stress is obtained = 2269.6 Mpa. The position variation of the parallel gripper is analyzed by performing the parallel gripper mechanism using ADAMS simulation. The results indicate that the parallel gripper possesses relatively good performance during in-hand manipulations and in-plane vertical transmission. In ADAMS simulation, while comparing in-plane horizontal and vertical transmission, the gripper performance is better in vertical motion transmission. Through dynamics analysis of ADAMS, the gripper mechanism carried out driving forces and torque variation curves. Optimization of the design variables of the gripper is done using GA. Fitness value= 0.0122666. The novelty of the mechanism is new performance index (Energy Manipulation Index) is used for optimization using GA. The stress analysis is still now not carried out on the mechanism.

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